

CHEMICAL CONSTITUENTS OF MOWRAH FLOWERS
(*B. LATIFOLIA*), PART III. PREPARATION OF SYRUP
AND ANALYSIS OF FLOWERS FROM
VARIOUS DISTRICTS

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Riche and Remoñt¹ reported that air-dried mowrah flowers contained 60% of sugars of which only one seventh was crystallisable. Fowler *et al.*² prepared a syrup from mowrah flower extract but could not remove an unpleasant flavour from it. Walawalkar prepared solids like jaggery by spraying the syrup on a hot aluminium plate. Abhyankar and Narayana⁴ reported that these flowers contained 76-83% of total sugars on a moisture-free basis. Of this 75-87% were reducing sugars. The syrup of 70-75° Brix, they obtained, had an acid reaction and contained 47.79% reducing sugar, 12.96% non-reducing sugar, 26.40% moisture and 12.90% non-sugar material.

Shroff⁵ analysed the mowrah flowers and prepared a syrup by treating the extract with norite, phosphoric acid and lime. He claimed that 80% of the colour was removed from the prepared syrup by these treatments. The syrup had an acid reaction and was sweet in taste. In the present communication, the syrup was prepared in three stages :

(i) Extraction : The flowers were extracted with either cold or hot distilled water or ethyl alcohol.

(ii) Clarification and defecation : Different reagents like lime, Mg salts, ion-exchange resins, animal and activated charcoal and H_2PO_4 were employed.

(iii) Concentration of the clarified mowrah flower extract : This was achieved by concentrating the extract in vacuum (10 mm.) at 50°.

Mowrah flowers obtained from various districts like Nasik, Nadiad, Himatnagar, Prantij, E. Khandesh and Godra were analysed for moisture, reducing and total sugars, crude protein, fat, ash and minerals like iron, calcium and phosphorus.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

Extraction. (i) With distilled water.—Flowers (100 g.) were blended with 500 ml. of distilled water for 3 to 5 minutes, macerated, the suspension heated to 60°-70° for a few minutes with constant stirring, cooled and centrifuged. The supernatant liquid was decanted and the residue discarded. Both the supernatant liquids were mixed and filtered. This final filtrate (10% extract) was used for clarification and defecation.

(ii) *With 95% alcohol.*—The flowers (100 g.) were blended with 300 ml. of ethanol for 3 minutes. This was filtered and the residue again taken up in 200 ml. of fresh ethanol, triturated and filtered. Both these filtrates were mixed together and the final filtrate was used for clarification.

Clarification and defecation were carried out by the addition of charcoal (animal or activated), lime and saturated solutions of MgO , $MgCO_3$ and $Mg_3(PO_4)_2$ to the known volume of the above 10% flower extract. After addition of the known amount of reagent, the mixture was allowed to stand for one hour with an occasional stirring, filtered, and made to volume. In the filtrate sugar concentration, pH and intensity of colour were noted. In some cases, CO_2 and SO_2 were passed through the filtrate after liming. Phosphoric acid was used after liming.

Ion-exchange resins.—Resins, 'Zeo-Karb 215' (cation exchanger) and "Deacidite B" (anion exchanger) were used. 'Zeo-Karb 215' was activated by passing 2 to 3 volumes of 2N-HCl till the elute was acidic. Then the resin was washed with distilled water till the elute did not show any turbidity with $AgNO_3$ (0.1N) solution. Deacidite B was activated by passing 2 to 3 volumes of 2N-NaOH till the elute was alkaline to litmus. Resin was then washed free of hydroxide. The elute had pH between 7 and 7.5.

Mowrah flower extract was first passed through the column of Deacidite B resin and then through 'Zeo-Karb 215' resin column. The final eluate was concentrated to obtain the syrup. The clarified extract was concentrated under vacuum (at 10 mm.) at 45°-50° till the liquid kept for evaporation contained 60-65% of sugar. The estimations of sugars, protein, fat, ash and minerals were carried out according to the methods described in previous communications⁶.

The aqueous extract of mowrah flowers (10%) was darker in colour having a peculiar odour. Alcoholic extract was somewhat lighter in colour and the peculiar odour was masked by the odour of ethanol itself

The clarification results by different agents are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

No.	Clarifying agents.	Minimum amt. for 100 ml. of 10% ext.	%Loss of sugar.	Colour of the soln.	Colour removed.
1.	Activated charcoal	2.0 g.	7.230	Very slightly yellow	82.85%
2.	Animal charcoal	5.0	4.665	Do	67.70
3.	Activated + animal charcoal (1 : 1)	3.5	5.600	Do	70.75
4.	Lime (solid)	6.25	20.51	Slightly yellow	43.45
5.	Saturated lime water	50 ml.	4.3%	Orange-yellow	50
6.	MgO	170	1.600	Yellow	39
7.	MgCO ₃	100	...	Intense yellow	21
8.	Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂	125	...	Do	15
9.	MgO : MgCO ₃ : Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ (3 : 1 : 1)	100	...	Do	36
10.	MgO : MgCO ₃ : Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ (2 : 1 : 1)	100	...	Do	25
11.	MgO : MgCO ₃ : Mg ₃ (PO ₄) ₂ (1 : 1 : 1)	100	...	Do	19

Table II shows the clarifying action of saturated Ca(OH)₂ solution and H₃PO₄ on 10% mowrah flower extract.

TABLE II

Vol. of 10% flower extract = 100 ml.							
No.	Ca(OH) ₂ added.	H ₃ PO ₄ added.	Colour of solution.	%Sugar.	%Loss of sugar.	p _H of soln.	Colorimet. reading.
1.	Intense yellow	38.76	...	4.0-4.5	375
2.	50 ml.	...	Reddish yellow	29.70	9.06	7.2-7.8	400
3.	50	5 ml.	Clear orange yellow	29.70	9.06	5.8-6.2	290

The loss in sugar percentage is due to the action of lime on sugar. The action of H₃PO₄ after liming is to precipitate excess of Ca(OH)₂. In doing so, it clarifies by taking some of the pigments or colouring matter.

From all these data, syrup was prepared by the following method. The flower extract (10%) was first treated with 2% activated charcoal with constant stirring for half an hour, filtered and passed through the activated ion-exchange resins. It was first passed through the anion exchanger and then through the cation exchanger. The filtrate, thus obtained, was again treated with 2% activated charcoal for 15 minutes and concentrated under vacuum at 10 mm. pressure, temperature being kept constant between 45° and 50°, to a syrup consistency. The analysis of the syrup is recorded in Table III.

TABLE III

	Observation.		Observation.
Colour ...	Golden yellow	Density ...	1.2108 g./c.c.
Odour ...	Odour of fresh mowrah flowers	Ref. index (28°)	1.46
Taste ...	Sweet (very slightly bitter at the end)	Sugar ...	61.0%
Mobility ...	Viscous	Ash ...	0.87%
Moisture ...	32.2%	Undetermined	5.03%

The percentage drop in the ash content is due to the use of ion-exchange resins.

Analysis of flowers from various districts.—Table IV shows the percentage composition of mowrah flowers from different districts of Bombay State.

TABLE IV*

Constituents.	Nasik.	Nadiad.	Himatnagar.	Godra.	E. Khandeash.	Prantij.
Moisture	21.6	21.5	19.49	18.11	19.45	19.21
Crude protein	4.945	4.089	6.594	6.260	5.120	4.004
Crude fat	1.288	0.926	1.205	1.191	1.150	1.040
Reducing sugar	52.28	55.20	49.85	54.95	49.21	50.21
Total sugar	70.31	70.10	67.12	69.52	65.72	66.65
Invert sugar	18.03	14.90	17.27	14.57	16.51	16.55
Ash	2.592	4.107	5.182	5.057	2.732	4.119
Phosphorus (mg.)	127.7	120.1	126.6	145.1	121.1	130.0
Iron (mg.)	30.41	47.49	21.50	30.70	22.27	35.91
Calcium (mg.)	250.7	268.4	235.9	226.8	177.3	255.2

*All these constituents except reducing, total and invert sugars, are expressed on moisture-free basis.

D I S C U S S I O N

Clarification by activated charcoal is one of the best methods. The drawback in purification of syrup, however, is that some quantity of sugar is also adsorbed on the surface of the charcoal powder, the loss being 7.23%. In case of bone charcoal, the loss of sugar is 4.7% but the amount of charcoal used is 2 to 3 times greater than the amount of activated charcoal to clarify the same volume of mowrah flowers to the same extent.

By the process of liming, most of the colouring matters, proteins, etc. were removed but at the same time a large amount of sugar was also destroyed. However, this was removed by using saturated lime water. Here the loss was approximately one third, but the volume increased. By the passage of CO₂ after liming, the colour was further removed. However, after a certain stage, when the gas was passed in excess, the solution again became darker in colour.

The action of saturated solutions of Mg salts like MgO, MgCO₃, and Mg₃(PO₄)₂, either alone or in combination, showed no appreciable change in colour intensity though there was negligible loss of sugar.

Ion-exchange resins, especially cation-exchange material, removed appreciable amount of the colouring matter. Not only they removed the colour but also the inorganic ions, which were not needed in the extract. Though the resins did not totally remove the ions, they removed an appreciable quantity by exchanging H⁺ or Na⁺ ions for cations and OH⁻ or Cl⁻ ions for anions.

Though basic lead acetate (as solid or as saturated solution) also clarifies to an appreciable extent, it cannot be used due to its toxic nature.

Gases like Cl₂ and SO₂ clarified to a little extent. These gases were passed into the extract after liming. On concentration after bubbling SO₂, a precipitate was deposited in the concentrated liquid. These gases are inadvisable in this case. This is in accordance with the observation of Walawalkar³.

The syrup was golden yellow in colour, sweet in taste (with a very slightly bitter taste at the end) and a flavour of fresh mowrah flowers. This slightly bitter taste may be due to the presence of tannins, tannic acid and/or malic acid which might be present in traces. Ultraviolet and visible spectra of the syrup did not show any peak but showed general absorption. These denote that the syrup is pure and contains no impurity, which would show the characteristic absorption.

The alcoholic extract of mowrah flowers was yellow in colour and its spectra showed a general absorption. On concentrating under vacuum at 10 mm. pressure, it formed into a thick viscous liquid which ultimately solidified to a yellowish white mass. This mass gave the same characteristics as exhibited by the syrup.

When this mass or syrup or the extract itself was left exposed to the atmosphere, rapid development of fungi and moulds had taken place, indicating their utilisability as a substrate in microbial fermentation.

If the syrup is further concentrated in vacuum under the same condition, a mass like jaggery forms but no crystallisation takes place.

From Table IV, it can be shown that in general the variation in the total sugar percentage is from 65 to 70. The reducing sugar ranges from 48-55% and the invert sugar from 14-18%. Flowers from Himatnagar and Godra

contained high amount of crude protein and ash content. Flowers from Godra and Prantij had a high percentage of phosphorus, while Nadiad variety had high percentages of iron and calcium, and East Khandesh variety was low in iron and calcium.

S U M M A R Y

Different methods of extraction, clarification and defecation were employed for the preparation of mowrah flower syrup. The best clarifying agent was activated charcoal which removed colour to the extent of 82 to 85%. The ion-exchange resins were employed for the clarification of the extract. The syrup had 61% sugar and an acceptable sweet taste.

Mowrah flowers from various districts of Bombay province had been analysed for their sugar and mineral contents.

R E F E R E N C E S

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